

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PROTECTING YOUNG PEOPLE FROM VARIOUS INFORMATION THREATS

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Abstract. *Today, the consciousness of young people is negatively affected by information in various ways. Media magnates in particular are controlling the human worldview through information. Indeed, by the beginning of the 20th century, such concepts as "information age", "informed society", "information attack" appeared in our lives. This is evidenced by the increased importance of the concept of information today, the expansion of coverage, the change in purpose and purpose. This article provides feedback and insights into the psychological aspects of protecting young people from various information threats.*

Keywords: *youth, information threats, psychological aspects, spirituality, information society, information attack, information concept.*

Introduction. Information is now moving away from the meaning of reporting on a process, reality or event, and becoming a propagandist of influencing the minds and hearts of people, the laws and regulations existing in society, and the emergence of universal values and concepts, united around a specific goal recognized by the whole world in the interests of certain groups and communities; political, economic, military, as a result of human development, at the same time, the impact of information on social consciousness and its negative consequences have become one of the serious problems of society.

Now, as a result of the attack on the human mind by means of the weapon called information, the modern forms of "war" have arisen, which have to do with taking over his thinking and mind, to serve the purposes of the powers that unite them. their audience around an idea by increasing their power by expanding. By the time of development, a serious struggle is raging for a worthy place in the information space of the world, which does not have a material appearance and form, but can only be seen and understood with the mind. According to experts in the field, under the concept of information weapons lies a certain system of special disinformation technological tools that have a negative impact on the nation's mentality, culture, spirituality, religion, information and military system of the state.

Satisfying the need for information is a positive situation, but it is worrying that young people are being deceived by information that has no basis, which seems innocent at first glance, but has a malicious purpose. Information has moved away from the meaning of informing about a process, reality or event, and it is a certain group united around a specific goal of influencing the mind and spirit of people, the laws and regulations existing in society and the universal values and concepts recognized by the whole world. and to bring forth unique new interpretations that serve the interests of communities; becoming a promoter of political, economic, military, religious and other views.

As a result, at the current stage of human development, the impact of information on mass psychology and its negative consequences have become one of the serious problems of society. Now, as a result of attacking the human mind with the so-called weapon of information, modern

forms of "war" have emerged, which are related to capturing his thinking and intellect, expanding his audience and increasing his power, and making them serve the goals of the forces united around some idea. It's done.

At the current stage of development, a serious struggle is raging for a worthy place in the world's information space, which does not have a material appearance and form, but can only be seen with the mind and thought. According to experts in the field, under the concept of information weapons lies a certain system of special disinformation technological tools that have a negative impact on the mentality, culture, spirituality, religion, information and military system of a nation, nation.

The analysis of scientific sources shows that media influence has its own scientific concept, which is based on theories such as "Theory of personality and social relations", "Threat detection and response". It can be noted that regional, ethno cultural, religious, political and economic factors are used in the implementation of psychological influence. Psychological influence has constructive and destructive aspects. Its constructive aspect will gain more practical importance and will be directly aimed at ensuring the effectiveness of the implementation of the country's strategy. It is the implementation of a set of programmatic activities carried out through various methods and tools in order to give positive instructions to citizens in order to form a security culture, to inculcate the main principles of national development ideas, and to smooth out social deviations that can be expressed in society. [157. 48-b]

Psychological influence has its own ideology and is distinguished by its orientation to a specific object. It can be divided into *two groups* in terms of the purpose of influence. In this case, each group can be distinguished not only in terms of its task and purpose, but also in terms of its character and direction, to have an *internal psychological* effect and to have an *external psychological* effect.

Internal psychological impact. It can be carried out in order to implement the state strategy, in order to form important visions and regulations, and to implement social activity.

External psychological influence is carried out on the basis of the concept of the state's foreign policy, aimed at raising the country's image in the international arena, creating a basis for international cooperation at various levels.

They include psychological properties, which include:

- attract attention;
- ideological task (sense of the situation: what problems need to be solved and ways to solve them);
- to convince the audience of the correctness of the problems and the proposed ways to solve them;
- mobilizing the audience to support the author's proposals.

It is known that social-psychological security of a person and threats arising (possible) in this regard appear on the basis of external and internal influences, which can be shown as follows:

- the social environment that can have a negative impact on personal safety (including: various emergency situations, criminal environment, unemployment, etc.);
- causing danger to others based on the effects of negative individual-psychological characteristics of a person (for example, telephone terrorism, sadism, premeditated aggression, etc.);

- under the influence of a person's socio-psychological qualities (simplicity, trustworthiness, etc.), he creates a danger for himself (suicide, becoming a victim of the deception of some destructive groups) [156.91-b].

These situations, in turn, can lead to the following consequences of a tragic nature: a narrowing of the circle of social communication, a change in the content of values, living only for today and not thinking about the future, deformation of the figure of "I", the occurrence of psychological depression. (internal instability, internal conflict, feeling of loneliness, social fear, accentuation of personal character). Ideological immunity acts as a protective shell in order not to fall into negative socio-psychological situations and performs the following tasks:

- first, it "limits" the level of consciousness of young people from negative and painful experiences, balances the relationship between their inner world and their current mental state;
- secondly, in order to free young people from emotional and informational stress, it provides psychological regulation, ensures that they do not perceive threatening messages and information, and do not fall under their influence;
- thirdly, it acts to protect young people from psychological instability and fulfill their intrapersonal location.

Conclusion. The concept of information today is gaining a wider meaning and meaning than ever before. Today, in the time and space we live in, the so-called "information attack" weapon, which acts sometimes openly, in most cases covertly, without depending on us, has appeared, and with the help of this weapon, the possibility of possessing the human mind is now emerging. Preventing and protecting the psychology of our people, especially the young generation, and forming immunity against "information attack" is an ever more urgent issue.

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